

Forder Bridge Project, Paulding County (41.21932, -84.67270)

Since construction in 2021, the main nutrient benefit of the Forder Bridge Project has been filtering nutrients delivered from a culvert (tile drain). The whole parcel drains an agricultural field (7.3 acres), forested plot (6.2 acres), and residential area (1 acre). Nutrient retention estimates were improved in 2024 by communication with local partners with a better understanding of the drainage area of the site. The culvert-fed flow-through treatment train is the main contributor to new nutrient retention, whereas the river-adjacent pools flooded only one or two times in 2023 and 2024. The Project filtered 1.5 lbs phosphorus per acre in 2024, in addition to the runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source (0.7 lbs phosphorus per acre each year). The vegetation nutrient stock at this Project was 111 lbs phosphorus per acre for aboveground and 4.5 lbs phosphorus per acre for belowground biomass.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology of this Project is passively managed. The Project has 5 acres of restored wetland, including multiple wetland features: a culvert-fed treatment train (Complex 4), elevated pools adjacent to the Maumee River (Complex 2), and sets of depressional pools fed only by surface water (Complexes 1 and 3). Water from land southeast of the Project enters the treatment train from a culvert during storm events. Each treatment train pool passively flows into the next and eventually into a small stream that delivers water to the Maumee River. The elevated riverbank pools and the depressional pools primarily receive water from only surface runoff. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm event in which flow is expected through the culvert that feeds the treatment train.

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar tile-fed and treatment train wetlands or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Diverting water from the treatment train and/or the Maumee into the disconnected depressional pools (Complexes 1-3) could increase the capacity for nutrient removal, but the elevation of these features in comparison to the Maumee River would likely make this prohibitively costly.
- It is important to accurately assess connectivity to water and nutrient sources by engaging in dialogue with on-the-ground local experts to estimate drainage area, in addition to using available tools like USGS StreamStats.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.